
Benefits of Multidisciplinary Education in Performing Arts

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ABSTRACT

The national education policy (NEP) 2020 emphasizes the importance of multidisciplinary education and incorporating Performing arts. The NEP recommends that students learn about multiple arts, performing arts, visual arts, such as music, dance and drama, can help students develop self-expression and respect to others. Multidisciplinary education in performing arts is a holistic approach to learning that combines performing arts with other subjects to help students develop a variety of skills. This article to promote children to express themselves and develop their creativity in unique ways.

INTRODUCTION: Importance of education is the transmission of knowledge. The term education can denote the mental states and qualities of educated individuals and the academic field studying educational phenomena. Essentially education socializes children into society by instilling cultural values and norms, equipping them with the skills necessary to become productive members of society. It stimulates economic growth and raises awareness of local and global problems. Organized institutions play a significant role in education.

CONCEPT OF MULTIDISCIPLINARY EDUCATION:

Multidisciplinary education is a form of learning that integrates various subjects to provide a comprehensive educational experience. A multidisciplinary education, as envisaged in the NEP 2020 aims to develop social, physical, intellectual, emotional and moral capacities of human beings in an integrated manner. Multidisciplinary education prepares students to develop deeper skills and approach problems with broader perspectives.

Multidisciplinary is where two or more academic disciplines collaborate specific purpose. A multidisciplinary approach in education is a way of learning which gives a major focus on diverse perspective and different disciplines of learning to illustrate a theme concept of any issues. It is the one in which the same concept is learned through multiple viewpoints of more than one discipline. Which approach combines knowledge and skills from several academic disciplines to address complex issues and difficulties.

The multidisciplinary approach in education is a method that integrates knowledge and skills from multiple disciplines to provide a comprehensive learning experience. It prepares students to develop deeper skills and approach problems with broader perspectives. It encourages students to draw connections between subjects, enhancing their critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Students able to identify and explain the various theoretical models within their chosen fields. It promotes innovation, adaptability, and a broader perspective, equipping graduates with the versatile skills need to thrive in diverse professional fields and address global issues effectively.

BENEFITS OF MULTIDISCIPLINARY EDUCATION:

Multidisciplinary education having many benefits. It studies offer numerous benefits, including broader perspective, studying multiple subjects simultaneously provides students with a broader perspective on various issues. This approach helps students connect the dots between different fields leading to a deeper understanding of complex problems. Which includes creative, collaboration, motivation and broader perspectives.

Multidisciplinary education integrates knowledge and methodology from various disciplines, fostering a holistic learning approach. It encourages students to draw connections between subjects, enhancing their critical thinking and problem-solving skills. Rather than studying each academic topic separately, a multidisciplinary approach focuses on connecting them. This method is necessary of effective teaching and learning. Today education, which combines insights and methods from multiple fields of study, is essential in fostering the versatile and adaptive thinkers needed to tackle these multifaceted issues.

Project based learning, incorporates real world projects that regular students to apply theoretical knowledge to practical scenarios.

Community immersion, integrating community immersion and engagement projects that align with course objectives, enabling students to learn and contribute to the society.

Collaborative learning, encourages group work and interdisciplinary projects to mirror workplace dynamic and challenges.

Faculty training and development, improves international institutes often invest heavily in faculty development to support multidisciplinary and experiential learning Indian institutions are improving in this area but still need to expand their efforts to match international standards.

Global exposure includes international models often include study abroad programs and global internship. Indian education can create partnership with foreign universities to offer exchange programs, giving students international exposure and a broader perspective.

ASSESSMENTS INNOVATION:

International models often use diverse assessment methods, including reflective journals. Peer reviews and project evaluations. Indian education can adopt these innovative assessments strategies to better evaluate experiential learning outcome. NEP2020 aims to develop social, physical, intellectual emotional and moral capacities of human beings in an integrated manner. The national education policy NEP 2020 aims to make higher education more multidisciplinary, holistic and inclusive. The policy encourages students to explore a wide range of subjects, including arts, humanities and vocational training and to develop a flexible curriculum based on their interests and aptitudes.

THE NATIONAL EDUCATION POLICY 2020:

The NEP 2020 was announced by the Indian government on July 29 2020 and is the first major change to the countries education policy since 1986. It provides high quality education to all prepare youth for national and global challenges and develop cognitive skills. Which helps to revise and revamp the education structure, promote critical things, creativity and innovation and internationalize education. Performing arts including music. Dance and drama play a crucial role in holistic education. The national education policy NEP 2020 emphasizes the importance of incorporating performing arts into school curriculums to foster creativity, critical thinking and emotional development performing arts contribute significantly to this holistic approach by encouraging self-expression and collaboration.

The NEP 2020 policy encourages integrating performing arts with academic subjects to enhance learning experiences. For ex – while music can be integrated into language learning through songs and rhythms. NEP 2020 advocates for a well-rounded education that nurtures students cognitive, emotional and social skills. Performing arts contribute significantly to this holistic approach by encouraging self-expression,

empathy and collaboration. Participating in performing arts teacher's student's effective communications and team work skills. These skills are essential for academic success and futures career opportunities.

CONCLUSION:

Integrating performing arts into school's curriculums aligns with the NEP 2020 version of holistic education b incorporating performing arts into both academic and extracurricular activity critical thinking and overall development.

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